

BLACKBERRY SEED OIL-LOADED PLA NANOFIBERS AS ACTIVE PACKAGING WITH UV ABSORBENT POTENTIAL

Aleksandra Miletić¹, Ljiljana Matović², Igor Karlovits², Branka Pilić¹

¹University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Technology, Novi Sad, Serbia

²University of Belgrade, Vinca Institute of Nuclear Sciences, Belgrade, Serbia

³Pulp and Paper Institute, Ljubljana, Slovenia

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alexm@uns.ac.rs

Abstract: *It is well-known that waste originating from food production can be a valuable raw material rich in active components. Concerning the latest trends in the circular economy, a waste-less economy with zero environmental impact, revalorization of the waste is highly recommended. Waste generation is very high in the industry of natural beverages since fruits and vegetables are pressed, and the amount of pomace leftover is enormous. These pomaces can be dried and further processed to extract valuable components, mainly antioxidants, used in food, cosmetics, packaging, etc. Cold-pressed blackberry seed oil (BSO) is a precious component derived from the dried seeds left from juice production. It has a high antioxidant content and high chlorophyll content (around 3000 mg/kg). It is rich in omega fatty acids, vitamins E and C, and has a very high carotenoids content (35-40 mg/kg). BSO has excellent UV absorption power and can be used in sunscreens. UV light can trigger chemical reactions that can produce free radicals and auto-oxidation of lipid-rich food, which can cause the change of the food quality and might induce the deterioration and discoloration of fresh meat, degradation of vitamins, and the development of off-flavors. In order to minimize the effect of UV irradiation on food quality, different UV filters and absorbers can be used, which can be incorporated into the packaging material. There are organic (benzophenones and benzotriazoles) and inorganic (titanium dioxide and zinc oxide) UV absorbers commonly used in food packaging. PLA-based nanofibrous films were prepared by loading an appropriate amount of BSO with potential use as UV absorbent packaging. Materials were characterized using mechanical,*

thermal, morphological, chemical, and application properties. The presence of BSO did not affect the properties of PLA when compared to pure PLA nanofibers, and material made this way can be successfully used as active packaging material for light-sensitive food.

Keywords: blackberry seed oil, PLA nanofibers, active packaging